
AUGUST 2020

PROJECT WEBSITE, APP & SOCIAL MEDIA TOOLS

SOLAR ENERGY FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

Deliverable D3.2
Project website, App and social media tools

WP3. Dissemination, Communication and Education

Lead Beneficiary ICIQ – Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia
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v 1.0	20 July 2020	Laura López, H. de Groot	Updates on monitoring and development of the different tools, according to review of the project.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The report Deliverable D3.2 describes the website created for external and internal communication. It delineates the motivation behind the concept of the website and names the parties responsible for the website and benefiting from it. The document firstly describes the content of the public section, highlighting the ideas and objectives behind it. Then, it shows the private section designed for the exchange of information between partners. The report also defines the social media tools used and the development of a new smartphone application focused on the sharing of scientific and technological information. The final aim of the document is to define the expected impact of these communication tools for the project consortium and the whole community.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Within HORIZON 2020 SUNRISE coordination and support action (CSA), a work package on Dissemination, Communication and Education (WP3) has been considered in order to carry out the internal and external activities related to the project in these areas. The main objectives of WP3, as described in the Grant Agreement, are to create consciousness of the project, stimulate dissemination of the project actions, organize dissemination activities and contribute to the creation and growing of a SUNRISE community. In order to meet these objectives, the available existing communication tools will be used, and a series of activities organized.

Deliverable D3.2 “Project website, App and social media tools” describes the key points of design, execution, content, usage, and communication strategy behind the internet platform of the SUNRISE large-scale research initiative.

The URL of the website is www.sunriseaction.eu and it has been online since September 20th, 2018. The website was first hosted and maintained by partner Université Catholique de Louvain, managed by Dr. Carina Faber until the beginning of May, 2019. The website was reworked, hosted and maintained from 6th of May, 2019, by partner Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia (ICIQ) and it will be weekly updated with the latest novelties. The social media accounts of SUNRISE were created between December 2018 and March 2019 on four platforms: Twitter (December 2018), Facebook (March 2019), LinkedIn (March 2019), and ResearchGate (February 2019). Both the website and social media networks constitute key communication tools to increase project visibility and impact towards industrial communities, researchers, policymakers, advocacy groups and general public. They are also key tools for sharing information between all SUNRISE partners. Additionally to already existing digital platforms, a smartphone App is currently under development for sharing scientific as well as technological contents among the SUNRISE community. The App is based on a system actually used in sports and news broadcasting and will be adapted to the needs of SUNRISE.

2. INTERESTED PARTIES

D3.2

Deliverable D3.2 is the responsibility of ICIQ as a part of the Work Package 3. The final version of the website was developed by an external company hired by ICIQ, Avellana digital, and shared with all consortium members for improvement before publication.

The role of both the website and social media networks is to provide information concerning the project to a very broad community. The following target groups have been identified:

The general scientific community and R&D industrial departments, – the European Commission, – journalists, general public and stakeholders, – companies in Energy, Oil&gas, Chemistry and Materials sectors (among others), – Venture Capital, – other private or public organizations.

The main objective of the website and social media networks is to successfully disseminate the activities and documents generated from all Work Packages during the lifetime of the initiative. Therefore, all partners are engaged with the website. In particular:

- 1) all consortium members are responsible for regularly contributing to the contents of the website;
- 2) consortium members are asked to share all the documents necessary for the project with the whole consortium via the Intranet (PLAZA);
- 3) consortium members are engaged to support the SUNRISE website by disseminating it through their own websites/social media.

3. COMMUNICATION TOOLS DEVELOPMENT AND DESCRIPTION

3.1. Website

SUNRISE website is accessible at: www.sunriseaction.eu and www.sunriseaction.com.

The platform has been created to serve as a project content management system on two levels: (1) external communication and dissemination of the project objectives and results, and (2) Internal Communication Platform within the consortium.

The SUNRISE public website was developed to act as an information hub about the project's aims, goals, activities and results. The website works as a prime public dissemination tool making available the project published results. The public section provides the following content:

- a) general information about the project, including initiative description and vision
- b) recent news about the project
- c) description of events organized within the framework of the project
- d) description of consortium members taking part in the project
- e) support materials and public deliverables
- f) press releases
- g) contact information and e-mail address (contact@sunriseaction.eu)
- h) supporters logos and community contributions
- i) blog
- j) links to social media
- k) appropriate acknowledgment and reference to the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme

The first SUNRISE website was designed to inform about the project and attract the attention of viewers to the content of the website and act as a repository of the different news, calls and events related to the initiative (Figure 1). Information about the project has been continuously generated and updated, maintained and adapted to the new designed web.

HOME | ABOUT | VISION | CONSORTIUM | More

SUNRISE

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

News for the SUNRISE community

Save the Date! SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop
10 April 2019

The next big event for the SUNRISE community will take place on 17 and 18 June 2019 in Brussels.

This meeting will serve to present the current state of our work, receive supporters' contribution to the Priority Research Direction of scientific topics, which will lead into the comprehensive Science & Technology Roadmap, and engage stakeholders on the governance of the future initiative.

The event will take place in connection with the [European State-of-the-Art Energy Week](#).

Stay tuned: the detailed agenda will follow soon. Register before 3 June!

REGISTRATION FORM

SUNRISE young researchers travel grant contest
01 April 2019

Are you a PhD student or postdoctoral researcher from the SUNRISE community? [Contact us](#) and [register](#)!

Are you going to any dissemination event (conference, symposium, etc.) to present your work about artificial photosynthesis?

Then check out the cases of the SUNRISE young researcher travel grant contest! You can win one of our grants! Deadline 20 April!

Up to 2 years since thesis defence.

BASES OF THE COMPETITION FORMS POSTER

The Times: Solar-driven CO₂ conversion to hydrocarbons
22 March 2019

As the Times reports in their recent article, [Scientists claim minimal fuel to make fuel from sunlight](#), a European collaboration has led to a photoelectrochemical (PEC) system for the reduction of CO₂ to ethylene and ethanol. The presented system uses copper-based catalysts (earth-abundant) at both electrodes of the electrocatalytic coupled to silicon-based perovskite PV cells. A full description of this approach has been published in the scientific journal [Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America](#). [Go to the article in the journal](#).

Congratulations to our supporting organisations involved: EPFL and ORF Solar Fuel!

SUNRISE Kick-off meeting
22 March 2019

The first SUNRISE partners gathered at the sunny premises (European Energy Research Institute).

The meeting focused on the latest advances of the different work packages, as well as on planning and discussing the many actions to come. Luckily, we started establishing our Priority Research Direction (PRD) which will be the basis of the Scientific and Technological roadmap. The latter will be one of the main outcomes of the SUNRISE CO₂ to be delivered at the end of the project. The next step is to involve the SUNRISE community in the mapping and defining of research needs, where supporters already had a first opportunity to join the discussion via a streamer session on Friday 22 of March.

SUNRISE CSA launched
01 March 2019

The first part of the SUNRISE journey, the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) has just started! Friday, 1st of March, has been the official launch for the fully-funded CSA!

The main objectives for our preparatory action are to:

- (i) Develop the R&D roadmap of a future European large-scale research initiative;
- (ii) Build the community (including scientific, industrial, and general public stakeholders);
- (iii) Establish an effective large-project governance scheme.

Help us to reach the goals. Be involved!

SUNRISE: successful proposal
01 February 2019

The SUNRISE project for a coordination and support action (CSA) has been successfully selected by the European Commission as one of the six candidates for a European large-scale research initiative. Within one year we will provide a complete design and description of the SUNRISE initiative, including the development of a technological roadmap and a planning structure, and the mobilization of industrial, academic and societal stakeholders. Be prepared - we will ask for your input and ideas!

OFFICIAL PRESS RELEASE

SUNRISE meeting in Brussels on November 15
15 November 2018

The SUNRISE consortium thanks all the participants for this very successful meeting. SUNRISE supporters and invited speakers made a great event with fruitful discussions on the project vision, mission and strategy. It was an important first step for building the SUNRISE community!

AGENDA

PRESENTATION J.C. | PRESENTATION | PRESENTATION SIEMENS
PRESENTATION | PRESENTATION C | PRESENTATION CSA

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 816336.

Figure 1. Landing page of SUNRISE first website

D3.2

In the new designed web, reshaped once the project was approved, the landing page is designed to attract the attention of viewers by exposing the project logo and banner, listing the content of the website (Figure 2).

All sections of the website have on top the SUNRISE logo and the menu bar enabling quick orientation through the search. All sections also provide addressing and contact information, reference to Horizon 2020 and European Commission (EC) support and a disclaimer excluding EC responsibility (once the project was approved).

The General info page presents the project at a glance, describes its objectives and highlights news and events.

Figure 2. Landing page

D3.2

The About us section provides information about the SUNRISE initiative (Figure 3.1), the large-scale project’s vision (Figure 3.2), and a list of all partner institutions taking part in the project (Figure 3.3), linking to their short descriptions. Every partner will be briefly described in terms of research quality, groups participating in SUNRISE and people responsible for the project.

The screenshot displays the 'About us' section of the SUNRISE Initiative website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the SUNRISE logo and links for 'About us', 'Newsroom', 'Blog', 'Support us', and 'Media'. Below this, the main heading reads 'SUNRISE Initiative'. A sub-heading states 'SUNRISE is one of six candidates for a future European large-scale research initiative. We propose a sustainable alternative to the fossil-based energy intensive production of fuels and base chemicals. The needed energy will be generated by sunlight. The raw materials will be produced sustainably (available in the atmosphere, such as carbon dioxide, water and hydrogen)'. A paragraph follows describing the project's goal to develop a sustainable energy and chemical production process. Below this, a blue box contains the text 'SUNRISE Candidate for a European large-scale research initiative'. The next section is titled 'Why SUNRISE is a large-scale enterprise' and lists several key points:

- It addresses the most dramatic problem now faced by mankind: anthropogenic climate change.
- It proposes radically new solutions for solar energy conversion and storage.
- It has highly ambitious S&T and cost targets to be implemented by top industrial players.
- It targets an essential change of the energy/industrial paradigms towards a circular economy.
- It has a broad approach towards the replacement of fossil fuels, providing solutions for industry ambivalence in both the energy and the chemical sector with zero or negative CO2 emissions.
- It ensures competitiveness of the industrial system despite stringent climate policy.
- It relies on a solid partnership between academia and industry.
- It develops an open structure, where the civil society contributes to the strategy together with scientists and engineers.
- It allows to create economically and ecologically efficient industrial symbiosis generating value locally.
- It is committed to foster education on energy and materials efficiency at all levels, a key prerequisite for a sustainable society.
- It will prepare a solid roadmap and blueprint right away (i.e. within 2020), which is necessary in view of the urgency of the problems to be solved.
- It is ready to cooperate with national and regional initiatives.
- Its targets are perfectly suited to establish synergies with a number of key EU projects/programmes, such as those on climate change, batteries, smart cities, high performance computing, and so on.
- It is open to cooperate with other CSA proposals.
- It has obtained the support of more than 100 players from academia, industry and society, including NGOs and global players in the energy, chemical, and automotive sectors. The backbone of the SUNRISE initiative is already outlined.

A 'Download information' button is located below the list. The next section is titled 'SUNRISE: Building a strong interdisciplinary community' and describes the project's goal to create a collaborative, long-term sustained effort involving academia, industry and society at large. Below this, a blue box contains the text 'The ambitious goals of the SUNRISE initiative can only be achieved through a collaborative, long-term sustained effort involving academia, industry and society at large.' The following text describes the first step to form a SUNRISE community, which took place on 5th of November 2018 in Brussels. The final paragraph of the screenshot states: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 874328. c/o Leibniz University, Eupatonweg 39 22525 CC Luderz, The Netherlands contact@sunriseinitiative.com Follow us Support us'. A disclaimer at the bottom states: 'Disclaimer regarding Agency responsibility: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 874328. The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained herein. SUNRISE Consortium acknowledges the contribution of Corine Faber in the opening of the initiative's first website.'

Figure 3.1. SUNRISE initiative page

Follow us [f](#) [t](#) [y](#) [v](#)

Sunrise

[About us](#) | [Research](#) | [Blog](#) | [Support us](#) | [Media](#)

Vision

Sustainable fuels and chemicals with solar energy and CO₂

Today's Challenge

Significant research and development efforts are urgently needed. Technologies for the transition to a low-emission society are not available on a large-scale level.

With the Paris climate agreement, the European member states engaged to mitigate global warming and to play a leading role in the fight against climate change. Recent IPCC reports point out the necessity to reduce carbon dioxide emissions to zero in the second half of the 21st century at latest. Technologies allowing the transition to a low-emission society are still not available on a large-scale level and significant research and development efforts are crucially needed.

The exponential increase of wind and photovoltaic capacity worldwide shows that a conventional alternative to fossil energy carriers already exists for electricity production. However, storing efficiently and reliably surplus electric energy remains one of today's top challenges. Storage processes converting electricity and solar energy into chemical energy would be highly desirable.

For the transport and heating sector, fossil fuels are an unmatched energy source, corresponding with the huge existing infrastructure. Also chemical industry accepts a variety of indispensable basic chemicals for every day life like hydrogen peroxide and ammonia, is completely dependent on fossil-based raw materials such as crude oil. Generating alternative basic and chemical raw materials from renewable energy sources represents a game changer and one of today's biggest challenges.

Sunrise Mission

Our goal is to provide a sustainable alternative to the fossil-based, energy-intensive production of fuels and basic chemicals. The needed energy will be provided by sunlight, the raw materials will be molecules abundantly available in the atmosphere, such as carbon dioxide, oxygen and nitrogen.

SUNRISE's ambition is to convert up to 2000 tons of CO₂ and to produce more than 100 tons of commodity chemicals per hectare per year, requiring a 30% energy gain over present best practices and deploying devices on the 1000 hectare scale by 2025. This requires raw materials for absorbing more than 10% of light and storing more than 30% of the photo-generated electrons in fuels or chemicals. With an unprecedented approach, SUNRISE will overcome the historic hurdle of the conversion of atmospheric CO₂ via far-red photons. Over the running span of 10 years, from 2022 to 2032, the flagship ambition:

- Reach an operational production cost level of 0.4 €/t, for fuel with competitive manufacturing of key enabling technologies.
- Bring atmospheric CO₂ photoconversion to the prototype level in operational environments.

Short term

In the short/medium term, we primarily aim at a circular production of high-value chemicals using renewable electricity sources and waste carbon dioxide from industrial processes. Existing technologies with relatively high technology readiness (near now) to be optimized regarding their efficiency, sustainability and/or scalability to industrial level, taking the example of water electrolysis driven by renewable electricity to produce hydrogen, more efficient catalyst materials are urgently needed to make this technology a true alternative. In the medium term, devices based on photoelectro catalysis permit to skip the primary step of electricity production through via photoelectro catalysis by converting solar energy, hydrogen and concentrated carbon dioxide directly into chemical products.

Long term

In the long term, the energy input for the chemical processes is provided by sunlight, which is directly converted into chemical products. Radically new approaches (based on photoelectrolysis/electrochemistry or biocatalysis) allow to transform diatomic carbon dioxide, nitrogen or oxygen from the atmosphere into chemical compounds, mimicking natural photosynthesis. The artificial leaf approach (which targets sustainable high-value chemicals that can be concentrated to any desired level, going beyond the natural photosynthesis processes with higher efficiency and a wide selection of target molecules).

Key enablers

Key enablers for such an artificial transition are information technology and new advanced materials. The former will enable optimized production processes, with savings of energy and feedstocks. New materials will allow cost-competitive, efficient and durable solutions across a number of renewable energy technologies. Given the interdisciplinary character of solar energy research and its intrinsic societal and economic implications, the flagship initiative requires key contributions from a wide spectrum of disciplines, including chemistry, biology, physics and engineering as well as social and environmental sciences and humanities.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019716

476 Leiden University - Eindhoven 55 2323 CC Leiden - The Netherlands
contact@sunrise.eu

Follow us [f](#) [t](#) [y](#) [v](#)
 Support us

Figure 3.2. SUNRISE's vision page

Follow us [f](#) [t](#) [in](#) [yt](#)

[About us](#) | [Newroom](#) | [Blog](#) | [Support us](#) | [Media](#)

Consortium

The SUNRISE proposal is conceived by a small consortium around Prof. Huub de Groot from Leiden University (Netherlands). High-ranking universities, Europe's largest research and technology organizations and industry join forces to elaborate a realistic and yet highly ambitious roadmap towards a zero-emission society. We believe that such a challenge can only be successful in a well-equilibrated approach between fundamental, applied and industrial research. Top scientists from multiple disciplines and a strong and efficient coordination between them are crucial to develop the technologies for the society of tomorrow.

Universities

Research and technology organizations

Industry

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 856256.

c/o Leiden University - Einsteinweg 55 2333 CC Leiden - The Netherlands
contact@sunriseconsortium.eu

Follow us [f](#) [t](#) [in](#) [yt](#)

Support us

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SUNRISE Consortium acknowledges the contribution of Corina Felzer in the opening of the initiative's first website.

Figure 3.3. Consortium page

The Newsroom section provides the current information about advances in the field, recent meetings, and public deliverables in the form of News (Figure 4.1). It also offers information about related events (Figure 4.2), opportunities (Figure 4.3), and useful resources, such as publications, videos, and infographics. Besides, it links the most important new content from the blog section.

Figure 4.1. News page

Figure 4.2. Events page

Figure 4.3. Opportunities page

The Blog page will include a live blog developed by a communication company, [Tickaroo](#), where supporters and followers will be invited to send their news and stories. It is intended to be an interactive part of the web where experts could also answer common questions.

The “Support us” page (Figure 5) is a call dedicated to research community industry sector, policymakers, and advocacy groups including citizens and students, as well as NGOs and associations dedicated to sustainable and renewable technologies and solar conversion applications who might be interested in being supporters of the initiative. It also displays a banner with all the current supporters, which will be regularly updated when new support letters are received.

This page will also serve as an interaction site where followers and supporters could reach the consortium with their ideas. For this contact form, as well as for the subscription to the public newsletter, a GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) compliance form will display.

Follow us

About us | Newsroom | Blog | Support us | Media

Support us

Your Support

SUNRISE gained the support of various stakeholders all over Europe. We are inclusive and curious to hear about your ideas! With your support, you help to bring forward the great public interest in the SUNRISE vision: the sustainable production of fuels and commodity chemicals at affordable costs of materials and Earth surface using solar energy.

Tell us about your ideas!

Name e-mail address

Your message

9 + 3 =

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 816336.

 c/o Leiden University - Einsteinweg 55 2333 CC Leiden - The Netherlands

 contact@sunriseaction.eu

 Follow us

 Support us

Disclaimer: evaluating Agency responsibility

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SUNRISE Consortium acknowledges the contribution of Calina Faber in the opening of the initiative's first website.

Figure 5. Support us

The Media section (Figure 6) records all the materials published about SUNRISE project. These include both press releases from SUNRISE in the media, and news from partners.

Figure 6. Media page

Finally, the consortium has an intranet page to share all the relevant information among all partners. The intranet used, PLAZA, has been developed by M2I (Materials Innovation Institute), the organization in charge of SUNRISE project’s management, within the management team. This is an internal tool they have developed to share information with partners in their multiple projects.

A direct link to the intranet is found in the home page, with restricted access to validated users (Fig 7). Partners can find all the information relevant to the development of the project organized in different folders (Fig 8).

Figure 7. Logon on the PLAZA system

Figure 8. Files distribution for SUNRISE project within the PLAZA system

3.2. Social media networks

The four SUNRISE social and professional media networks aim at spreading and disseminating the latest information about advances in the field, recent meetings, and public deliverables. They also offer information about related events, opportunities, and useful resources, such as publications, videos, and infographics. Besides, they serve as means of communication with the general audience, as they can contact SUNRISE team via the four different channels.

Facebook page

It serves to promote the initiative’s actions. It has a more formal tone and emphasizes SUNRISE news. It also promotes other external related items (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Facebook page

Twitter page

It serves to boost the project’s visibility among the general audience, researchers, companies and partners, massively, and interact with them (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Twitter page

LinkedIn page

It serves to boost the project's visibility among the scientific community. It emphasizes both SUNRISE news, and scientific papers related to the field (Figure 12).

Project

SUNRISE - Solar Energy for a Circular Economy (EU H2020 CSA, Ref. 816336)

Artur Braun · Eva-Mari Aro · Huub De Groot · [Show all 32 collaborators](#)

Goal: We propose a sustainable alternative to the fossil-based, energy-intensive production of fuels and base chemicals. The needed energy will be provided by sunlight, the raw materials will be water and other molecules abundantly available in the atmosphere, such as carbon dioxide,...

[Show details](#)

Updates 1 new 25

Recommendations 0 new 66

Followers 0 new 56

Reads 37 new 601

Overview **Project log** References (2) Questions

[Add research](#) [Add update](#) v

Project log

Build your reputation by sharing a project update

[Add update](#)

Amelia Ochoa
added an update 4d ago

Spring Meeting of the European Materials Research Society in Nice (France)

Happy to announce that SUNRISE will sponsor a poster prize at the 'Latest advances in solar fuels' symposium of the 'Spring Meeting of the European Materials Research Society' (E-MRS) on May 27-31, 2019 in Nice!

<https://www.european-mrs.com/latest-advances-solar-fuels-emrs>

[Comment](#) [Recommend](#) [Share](#)

Laura Lopez Suarez
at 12.83 · ICIQ Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia

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Artur Braun
added an update Apr 25

MRS Spring Meeting 2019 in Phoenix Arizona loaded with Artificial Photosynthesis contributions

In Spring 2009, Symposium S in San Francisco, was the first ever MRS Symposium on photoelectrochemical water splitting:

"Symposium S : Materials in Photocatalysis and Photoelectrochemistry for Environmental Applications and H2 Generation"

<https://www.mrs.org/spring2009/program-session/?code=S>

Now, 10 years after, solar photoelectrochemical energy storage and conversion lives on better than ever at MRS Meetings. There are more than one symposia relevant for PEC and AP.

The DoE PEC Working Group has organized Symposium ES11

<https://mrs.org/spring2019/symposium-sessions/symposium-sessions-detail?code=ES11>

"Symposium ES11 : Advanced Low Temperature Water-Splitting for Renewable Hydrogen Production via Electrochemical and Photoelectrochemical Processes"

There is an exciting selection of topics and speakers, including speakers from the SUNRISE project.

I encourage colleagues to think of making Symposia with the MRS also in the future.

[Comment](#) [Recommend](#) [Share](#) 3 Recommendations · 35 Reads

Figure 12. ResearchGate page

3.3. App

Fraunhofer is in charge of developing a new concept of application for smartphones devoted to the sharing of scientific information. The development is being done in cooperation with Tickaroo, a third partner. The key feature of the App will be the delivery of scientific and technological content in relationship to SUNRISE. Therefore, it will be possible to get access to cross-technological information, which boosts the SUNRISE developments as distribution pathways will be shortened. Qualified persons throughout all areas of science and engineering as well as economy will act as authors at the “author-end” of the SUNRISE App, while the whole SUNRISE-community acts at the “recipient-end”, therefore involving the overlap of the two groups.

This will provide the highest level of scientific openness required to ensure high-quality decisions as well as advice to the governance structure for impact-oriented actions in the large-scale initiative stage, including the avoidance of efforts being duplicated and the mitigation of intrinsic risks, for example risk of market failure.

At a first stage, the app will be internally designed and used within the consortium. Continuous user input will be collected to improve its performance, so at the end of the CSA a robust interface, useful for the scientific and industrial community will be developed. A first demonstrator will be ready to be presented during the [European Sustainable Energy Week](#). The SUNRISE consortium will be present at the Networking Village, with a stand where visitors could contribute to its development answering a short survey about how to improve the application and involvement of different sectors in the project. In Figures 13-15 the live blog system by Tickaroo is described visually.

Figure 13: The company tickaroo is providing the live content platform.

tickaroo
LIVE BLOG

FEATURES OF TICKAROO LIVE BLOG

Figure 14: Features of the tickaroo live blog system.

tickaroo
LIVE BLOG

LIVE BLOG STATISTICS

Figure 15: tickaroo offers the possibility to follow live blog statistics.

4. MONITORING, DEVELOPMENT, IMPACT & CONCLUSIONS

SUNRISE website is the main online tool to present and disseminate all the results and events under the framework of the project. It has been regularly updated by ICIQ in coordination with the management team in order to provide the latest news, relevant results and breakthroughs. It will remain available after the end of the CSA, at least until 3 years since the beginning of the action, as specified in the updated DMP (Data Management Plan, deliverable D3.4, an updated version is available attached to the Final Report, D5.3). Both the website and social media networks have been carefully designed to address the identified target groups in the most effective way, and it is the easiest way to ensure the visibility of the project for the EU as well as target audiences, consortium, stakeholders and general public. The expected outcome using an online communication strategy includes a large number of stakeholders being more aware of ideas and technologies for efficiently using and storing solar energy in the form of fuels and commodity chemicals. The SUNRISE website was designed as an interactive tool for public information and communication among partners and stakeholders. It will also be a repository for communication and training materials, deliverables and a work area for the project participants to share information between each other. It can be continuously improved and updated, in order to maximize the results and share them with target audiences.

The communication tools of the action have been continuously monitored, along with KPI (Key Performance Indicators). This monitoring and evaluation exercise is summarized in the Deliverable 3.1: Dissemination, Communication and Education plan and its Annex 1. The analysis has been done in two phases, a mid-term analysis, D3.1 delivered on October 2019, where the initial KPI were analysed and several changes and deviations were taken into account to update and propose new ones, and a final analysis based on these previous changes is included in the updated D3.1 annex, attached to the Final Report, D5.3. The updated D3.1 contains the main guidelines for a future Dissemination and Communication strategy, jointly developed with ENERGY-X in framework of the continuation action SUNERGY.

Overall, the dissemination, communication and education strategy and actions have been alive during all the action with continuous adaptation to provide optimal performance and interaction with the different audiences. Along the project, the resources page in the website has been continuously updated to serve as a repository containing useful materials created within the CSA (Figure 16). In addition, as appointed in the updated version of the DMP (D3.4), also a community has been created for the project in the zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sunrise/?page=1&size=20>, contributing to the openness of the initiative.

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Resources

VIDEOS

SUNRISE - Making Artificial Photosynthesis... RENEWABLE CLEAN FUELS WILL BE KEY

SUNRISE releases its technological roadmap to a clean-energy EU

[See more multimedia](#)

GRAPHIC MATERIALS

BREAKING DOWN THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY

SUNRISE Leaflet

SUNRISE Factsheet

[See more graphics](#)

NEWSLETTERS

#1 Newsletter - July 2019

#2 Newsletter - October 2019

#3 Newsletter - January 2020

#4 Newsletter - 19th March 2020

DOCUMENTS

SUNRISE Deliverables

Presentations

I want you to panic... and act

SUNRISE technological roadmap

Presentation team-Pascal van Veenendaal

[See more deliverables](#)

[See more presentations](#)

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SUNRISE Consortium acknowledges the contribution of Carina Faber in the opening of the initiative's first website.

Figure 16. Resources page with access to videos, graphic materials, newsletters, deliverables and presentations.

D3.2

As explained in the D3.1 and its Annex 1 (mid-term and final versions), social media, specific sections in the website, such as protected pages that were shared with consortium members and stakeholders to define the priority research directions, newsletters and e-mail campaigns have been key to involve stakeholders in the definition of key outcomes, in particular the roadmap (D1.2) and the blueprint (D1.3). Updated versions of both documents containing input from stakeholders are also attached to the Final Report, D5.3. Direct links to these documents are also available on the website, both in the News section and in the Deliverables section. The final Blueprint document offers a direct access to the community interested in developing solar resources, and includes information on research projects, initiatives on solar energy conversion and the circular economy, key research infrastructures, and actors in the field.

The SUNRISE social media channels were designed as appealing tools for public information and interaction with the different partners and stakeholders. They have also worked as hooks to promote the project and enhance visibility. They have been continuously improved and updated, in order to broaden the SUNRISE community and increase engagement. A thorough monitoring process was established, mapping main interactions between stakeholders and their interests (see mid-term and final versions of D3.1 and Annex 1 for a detailed explanation and revision). In that sense, the production of audiovisual materials has proven to be a powerful asset, and a Youtube channel was opened for the initiative. For the joint SUNERGY photo contest, a new Instagram account was created in December 2019. In addition, SUNERGY social media and website are running since March 2020.

Finally, the new App to be developed during the CSA aimed to explore a new concept for intersectoral scientific information exchange, contributing to the “Open Access” strategy. Advances and changes on its development are summarized in the D3.1 and its Annex 1 (both for the mid-term and final versions). During the CSA a demo version has been developed, available for the whole consortium under the link: <http://events.tickaroo.com/projectsunrise/> (the link has expired after the initial testing year, June 2019-June 2020, but it can be easily recovered and the content can be further developed at any time).

The demo was first presented at the SUNRISE stand during the Energy Week (EUSEW 2019). This first version is a test version, kept at minimum costs, a web App to get feedback from stand visitors, which were able to see that on a smartphone/tablet. At this first stage the App is thought to distribute relevant scientific content across different disciplines to encourage innovation and the main idea was to invite visitors to directly contribute to the App creation progress with their suggestions and opinions. Although visitors found interesting the idea of developing a smartphone application, most of them did not find appealing the initial content (a selection of publications and related projects), and suggested other content, for outreach and for training purposes, and addressed to general public users, by improving design and performance.

Based on that first external feedback, it seemed appropriate to further work on the initial idea and a following survey was prepared as an internal tool for consortium members to express their thoughts and preferences regarding further development of the application (Figure 17). This feedback is key to develop a future public version in a coming advanced development stage. According to the survey results the main aim of the application might be reformulated in future development, which will need further resources and time beyond the CSA stage, within a large

scale research and innovation project framework. The concept developed during this CSA project is intended to be a first step in this direction.

App evaluation

Please submit feedback regarding the demo of the SUNRISE App, designed to quickly and easily share the latest publications and news in the area.

1. Name (optional)

2. SUNRISE App

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Do you think that a developed version of this App will be useful for you?	<input type="radio"/>				
Would you like to receive the latest research news in your smart phone?	<input type="radio"/>				

3. What kind of information would you be interested to receive in your smart phone/tablet?

4. How would you improve the App? (Better design, search tool, comments section, etc.)

5. When do you think it would be the best moment to launch the App?

6. Do you think the App could be adapted to other type of content?

7. Any other comments

Figure 17. Distributed survey to consortium members regarding the App development and a visual graph on first questions answers.

Be a change maker & Join our community!

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